

Development of a Tool for Investigation of Child Leprosy Cases in Colombo RDHS Area

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Background

- Child leprosy indicates potential ongoing transmission and gaps in early detection and prevention.
- Detailed investigation of each case helps identify:
 - Sources of infection
 - Potential risk factors
 - Programmatic gaps
- A structured, standardized approach ensures uniform investigations, comprehensive data collection and meaningful conclusions from field findings.

Description of the initiative

- A comprehensive child leprosy case investigation tool was developed by the district team with technical guidance from the ALC
- Designed for district-level health staff to use during field investigations

Methods used for evaluation

- Implemented in district-level child leprosy investigations
- Monitored by district teams with the ALC
- Evaluation covered:
 - Data completeness & quality
 - Practicality in field use
 - Usefulness for decision-making
- Feedback from district and national reviewers confirmed its role in standardizing investigations
- Introduced at the Annual Leprosy Review – 5th Aug 2025

Results

- Eight child case investigations completed using the developed tool (as of 20th Oct 2025)
- Improved uniformity and completeness of district-level investigations.
- Enabled systematic recording of clinical details, social & environmental factors
- Aided identification of infection sources and programmatic gaps.
- Strengthened coordination between district teams and ALC, ensuring structured reporting and follow-up actions.

LEPROSY CHILD CASE INVESTIGATION FORM (Colombo RDHS)

1. Identification Details

- Name of Child: _____
- Age / Date of Birth: _____
- Sex (Male / Female): _____
- Religion: _____
- Grade: _____
- Health institution diagnosed: _____
- Place of residence: _____
- Type of Lesions (PDR, PLE, PML, PMS, PMSI, PMSII): _____

2. History and Source Investigation

- Any family member diagnosed with leprosy? (Yes/No) _____
- Relationship: _____
- Time of diagnosis: _____
- Type of Lesions (PDR, PLE, PML, PMS, PMSI, PMSII): _____
- History of prolonged contact with known leprosy cases in the community? (Yes/No) _____
- History of skin lesions / nerve involvement: (Yes/No) _____
- Duration of symptoms: _____

3. Clinical Assessment

- No. of skin lesions: _____
- Presence of disability: _____
- Eye: (Yes/No) _____
- Hand: (Yes/No) _____
- Foot: (Yes/No) _____
- Biomechanical status: _____
- Skin Sensation (Positive / Negative): _____
- SI: _____
- PI: _____

4. Household Investigation

- No. of household members: _____
- Any other household skin lesions or sensory involvement? (Yes/No) _____
- Have household contacts been examined? (Yes/No) _____

5. Contact Investigation

- Date of Contact Investigation: _____
- School / Community Investigation
- Was school screening conducted? (Yes/No) _____
- Date: _____
- No. of children examined: _____
- Are records maintained? (Yes/No) _____
- Yes, where to: _____

6. Treatment and Follow-up

- Treatment started on: _____
- Regimen used (MCP, PLE, PDR, etc.): _____
- Drug source (LPHS, Hospital): _____
- Adherence plan / SSI available: _____
- Follow-up date: _____

7. Contact tracing

Empty Contacts	School Contacts	Community Contacts

8. Remarks / Special Notes

Gaps identified on assessment / treatment compliance

Challenges

9. Investigation Done By:

- Name: _____
- Date: _____
- Signature: _____

Figure 1: Child Leprosy Investigation Tool

Lessons learnt

- The standardized tool strengthened district-level surveillance and response with ALC collaboration ensured its relevance and usability
- Future refinements from field experience will enhance its value and support better control of child leprosy transmission.